

ISic0186

I.Sicily inscription 0186

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Place and circumstances of discovery not recorded

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 15

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 13.5 cm

Width 16 cm

Depth 2.3 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---][i]acet [---]

2. [---]: Ioan(nes) : c[---]

Apparatus

Text after ILTermini with slight changes based on the photograph

Bivona: trace of final character could be B or D

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285326

EDR 127522

EDCS 8900407

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a

l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1980.0529

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 108

Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos*. 28-29: 3-29. At 22 no.74

Bivona, L 1975-1976. Nuove iscrizioni di Termini Imerese (Palermo). *Atti della Accademia di Scienze, Lettere e Arti di Palermo*. Ser.4, vol.35: 531-558. At 553 no.19 tav.9

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0186. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334474>